

4 Assessing sources and fractions of metals associated with 5 environmental plastics: a case study in Lake Como (Italy)

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8 Understanding of plastic-metal interactions is paramount to unveil the ecological risks of plastic pollution. Besides including
9 a (variable) amount of metal-containing additives, plastic objects can adsorb metals on their surfaces in the environment.
10 This work aims at measuring and assessing the possible origin of metals in environmental plastics deposited along the shores
11 of lake Como (Italy). Samples were characterized through Fourier-transformed infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and scanning
12 electron microscopy (SEM). Then, the total metal load was analysed by acid digestion. A direct extraction with nitric acid
13 was performed to detect labile metals and a three-step extraction scheme enabled the determination of physisorbed,
14 carbonate-bonded and organic matter-bonded metals, respectively. Eighteen metals (Al, Ti, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, As,
15 Sr, Ag, Cd, Sn, Ba, Pb and U) were analysed in total. Newly produced plastic items were also analysed as reference. Our
16 findings revealed that environmental samples retained a higher concentration of metals compared to virgin ones, especially
17 in the loosely bonded acid-extractable fractions, indicating their potential bioavailability. While some metals were
18 predominantly sorbed from the environment (e.g., Mn and Pb), others were mainly leached from plastic matrix (Ba, Cu and
19 Ti) or had a mixed origin (Zn, Fe, Sn, Sr and Al). This work shed light on the changes in bioavailability of metals induced by
20 plastic environmental ageing, set baseline values for a freshwater site, and provided insights of the potential bioavailability
21 exerted by metals associated to plastic litter.

22 1

23 Introduction

24 Plastic polymers are used in a great number of products and applications (e.g., industrial, agricultural and technological)
25 owing to their versatility, durability and low cost.¹ The short usage lifespan of most plastic articles in commerce and the
26 increasing production rates (worldwide production is expected to exceed 33 billion tons by 2050)²⁻⁴ led to the ubiquitous
27 accumulation of plastic in environmental matrices, despite the effort in some regions to improve waste disposal and
28 management.^{5,6} Microplastics (MPs), defined as plastic particles having size < 5 mm, are of foremost concern due to their
29 widespread distribution and potential environmental impacts.⁷ They have been found in various ecosystems, from water to
30 terrestrial and atmospheric compartments,⁸⁻¹⁰ as well as in food products for human consumption.¹¹⁻¹³

31 MPs can induce several direct negative effects on the biota, such as entanglement or cellular inflammation following
32 uptake.¹⁴⁻¹⁷ Still, other indirect and subtle effects which can pose ecosystems at risk are still not thoroughly understood.¹⁸ As
33 an example, MPs can act as vectors of inorganic species in the environment: ¹⁹⁻²¹ these particles can, in fact, adsorb and
34 accumulate metals from the surrounding media.^{22,23} Furthermore, plastic formulates contain metal-based additives which
35 are added with a variety of purposes, such as plasticizers, flame retardants, antioxidants, pigments and more.²⁴⁻²⁶ Many
36 metals express toxicity at low concentration and can severely threaten organisms at different trophic levels, leading to both
37 acute and chronic effects. Ingestion of metal-enriched plastic can possibly enhance their bioaccumulation.⁴

38 The sorption-desorption of metals on microplastics can be affected by various factors. Besides the polymer type and its
39 physicochemical features, a key role in the plastic-metal interaction is played by ageing processes.^{27,28} Naturally-aged
40 microplastics generally show a greater sorption of metals compared to pristine polymers.²⁹⁻³¹ Environmental ageing is also
41 observed to increase the leaching of metal-containing additives.³² Environmental factors (i.e., UV radiation exposure,
42 oxidative reactions, mechanical deterioration, and biofouling)^{23,33} indeed induce polymer embrittlement, increase surface
43 area and enhance polymer wettability. All these alterations enhance sorption and desorption of metals. Likewise, water
44 physicochemical conditions (such as pH, salinity, temperature, redox potential, suspended solids and dissolved organic

45 matter) affect the sorption and desorption processes.^{10,34–37} Given the complex framework governing the
46 sorption/desorption processes, unveiling the consequences for the ecosystem is challenging.^{35,38}
47 The analysis of metals on plastic samples collected from real environmental matrices can represent an initial step to assess
48 the relevance of this interaction in environmental settings and help in assessing the environmental risk posed by metal-
49 containing additives leaching from aged plastics, as well as the metals adsorbed on MPs from the environment. Several
50 approaches have been proposed to examine metals on plastic samples. Acid digestion with strong acid mixtures is still the
51 most employed method: it targets the total content of metals in plastic through the complete dissolution of the plastic
52 polymers. This approach does not allow to compare the chemical species sorbed on MPs and the metals present in the bulk
53 polymer, limiting the information for an effective bioavailability and exposure assessment.^{39–41} Thereby, other methods have
54 been applied to specifically investigate loosely-bonded or bioavailable fractions of metals, including single and sequential
55 extractions.^{29,42–46}
56 In our study we tested a comprehensive analytical approach including total acid digestion, single extraction and sequential
57 extractions to assess the metal content and fractionation on MP samples. This approach was performed on environmental
58 plastic litter found on the shores of Lake Como (Lombardy, Italy) and, for comparison, on equivalent pristine commercially

Fig. 1 Location map of Como Bay (panel a), as part of Lake Como (panel b), and Italy (panel c). The sampling site of environmental samples (Villa Geno) is highlighted with a blue cross. Sources: Google satellite images overlapped with the official state cartography (scale 1:25.000) provided by IGMI (Italian Army's Geographic Supporting Office).

59 available plastic objects obtained from local grocery stores. The comparison between pristine and environmental samples
60 helps to size the metal pool originally present in the plastic formulates and, by comparison, the potential changes in
61 (bio)availability (i.e., the release from the polymer matrix or the sorption from the environment). In addition, we investigated
62 the role of plastic properties and environmental aging in the changes of metal availability through their characterization using
63 Fourier-transformed infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). This study focuses on a
64 freshwater body since freshwater ecosystems have recently been appointed as sinks for MPs, but they are still limitedly
65 studied concerning the interaction of MPs and metals.^{39,47–49} Data associated with these environments are therefore limited
66 and fragmented.^{50,51}

67 2 Material and methods

68 2.1 Study area

69 The study area for the collection of environmental plastic and water samples encompassed Como shores (Italy). This site is
70 located at the end of the southwestern branch of Como Lake, a glacial, meso-eutrophic lake in northern Italy.^{52,53} Water
71 chemistry in Lake Como is dominated by magnesium, calcium and carbonate ions.⁵⁴

72 In this part the lake has no effluents. Two main streams (Valduce and Cosia), instead, drain from Como city to the lake. The
73 main sources of plastic litter in the Bay were observed to be direct littering in the beaches and longitudinal transport of
74 floating litter from the northern part of the lake induced by local winds.⁵⁵ We collected plastic litter samples around Villa
75 Geno (45.823° N, 9.076° E, Fig. 1) since this site was observed to be a major hot spot of plastic litter in the area.⁵⁵

77 2.2 Plastic samples collection and pre-treatments

78 In this study environmental and pristine macroscopic plastic objects and fragments (>5 mm) were used to generate simulated
79 MPs. This approach enables the analysis of abundant and homogenous sample in the MP size range, which in turn open the
80 way to analyse both the total amount of metals and the fractionation through direct and sequential extractions from a single
81 sample.⁴⁶

82 We manually collected macroscopic plastic fragments characterized by a visible advanced ageing state. Sample collection was
83 done wearing nitrile gloves and the samples were stored in virgin polyethylene (PE) bags to avoid metal contamination. Once
84 in laboratory, environmental samples were sorted according to the object category of litter (e.g., bottles, glasses, caps, toys,
85 packaging), colour and polymer type. The latter was assigned after visual sorting in case recycling codes were still visible and
86 validated through FTIR analysis (see section 2.4).

87 Samples of virgin plastics were obtained from new plastic objects representative of the same categories, colour, and polymer
88 type. These samples were analysed in order to: i) evaluate the concentrations of metals voluntarily used as additives in new
89 objects during manufacturing, and ii) control potential contamination during sample processing.

90 All plastic samples (virgin and environmental) were processed in the same way. They were first rinsed with ultrapure water
91 to remove other solids loosely attached to the surface (e.g., sand) and air dried for approximately 24 hours. Samples were
92 then cut into smaller pieces, grinded with a commercial mixer with stainless-steel blades, and sieved to <2 mm. This treatment
93 yielded sufficient quantities of homogeneous samples in the form of fragments with the size scale of MPs (<5 mm), needed
94 for the following analytical steps. In total, 3 samples of PE, 3 of polypropylene (PP) and 3 of polyethylene terephthalate (PET)
95 were prepared for metal analysis. For every polymer category, one pristine and two environmental samples were considered
96 (Table 1).

97 **Table 1** List of samples and their characteristics, including: their type (virgin or environmental), object category, colour, and polymer type.

Polymer type	Sample label	Type of sample	Item	Colour
PE	PEvir1	Virgin	Cap	Blue, green, and white
	PEenv2	Environmental	Cap	Blue, green, and white
	PEenv3	Environmental	Vase	Grey
PP	PPvir1	Virgin	Cup	Transparent
	PPenv2	Environmental	Cup	Transparent
	PPenv3	Environmental	Cup	White
PET	PETvir1	Virgin	Bottle	Transparent
	PETenv2	Environmental	Bottle	Transparent
	PETenv3	Environmental	Bottle	Transparent

99 2.3 Plastic samples characterization

100 Samples were analysed for specific surface functional groups with a Thermo Scientific™ (Waltham, MA, USA) Nicolet™ iS™ 10
101 attenuated total reflectance FTIR spectroscope, in order to: i) determine the polymer composition and ii) assess the level of
102 environmental ageing and biofilm development. Thirty-two scans were performed for every sample in the 4000 cm⁻¹ -
103 650 cm⁻¹ spectral interval, with a resolution of 0.482 cm⁻¹. A background spectrum was recorded prior to every
104 measurement. All collected FTIR spectra were smoothed using Savitzky–Golay filter (30 points of the window) and normalized
105 on the maximum absorbance peak using Origin 2018 software (OriginLab Corporation). A range of indexes were calculated
106 for a quantitative comparison of FTIR data. The following generalized equation was applied for calculating the indexes of
107 different functional groups:

$$108 \quad I_i = \frac{A_i}{A_{ref}}$$

109 in which I_i represents the index for the surface group analysed, namely the carbonyl group at 1715 cm⁻¹, hydroxyl groups at
110 3500 cm⁻¹, amides at 1650 cm⁻¹, and polysaccharides at 1040 cm⁻¹. A_i is the absorbance value at the specific wavelength,
111 whereas A_{ref} stands for the absorbance values at specific reference bands selected for the different polymer types: the C-H
112 band at 1465 cm⁻¹ for PE,⁵⁶ the reference peak at 1892 cm⁻¹ for PP,⁵⁷ and the band absorbing at 721 cm⁻¹ for PET.⁵⁸

113 In addition to FTIR spectra, SEM images were collected to examine the surface micromorphology using a Philips®
114 (Netherlands) Field Emission Gun-Scanning Electron Microscope (FEG-SEM), with a 20 keV beam under high vacuum
115 conditions. Before analysis samples were made more conductive by covering them with a gold layer using a Cressington (UK)
116 108 auto vacuum sputter coater.

117

118 **2.4 Metal analyses**

119 The total metal concentration in all plastic samples was assessed by acid digestion.^{44,59} Approximately 60 milligrams of the
120 prepared sample were weighted and put into a Teflon vessel, where 4 mL of ultrapure concentrated nitric acid were added.
121 The vessels were placed in a microwave oven (Milestone ETHOS One), with a 10 minutes initial heating up to 180 °C and a
122 following isotherm of 15 minutes. After digestion, the solutions were transferred into LDPE bottles, diluted with ultrapure
123 water and stored at 4 °C in a refrigerator.

124 An extraction with ultrapure nitric acid (HNO₃) 2% v/v in ultrasonic bath for 10 minutes at 120W was also applied to desorb
125 all loosely bonded metals.²⁷ In addition, a specific and recently proposed sequential extraction scheme was performed on
126 the samples to analyse three different metal fractions on MPs: i) the physisorbed and readily soluble fraction of metals with
127 ammonium nitrate 1M;⁶⁰ ii) the acid-soluble fraction of metals with acid acetic 0.1M; and iii) the oxidable and bonded to
128 organic matter fraction of metals with hydrogen peroxide 30% v/v. The detailed description of this methodology is available
129 elsewhere.⁴⁶

130 Solutions obtained by acid digestions and different extraction methods were analysed through Inductively Coupled Plasma –
131 Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS Thermo Scientific™ Icap-Q, USA) for the detection and quantification of 18 metals, namely:
132 aluminium (Al), titanium (Ti), vanadium (V), chromium (Cr), manganese (Mn), iron (Fe), cobalt (Co), nickel (Ni), copper (Cu),
133 zinc (Zn), arsenic (As), strontium (Sr), silver (Ag), cadmium (Cd), tin (Sn), barium (Ba), lead (Pb) and uranium (U).

134

135 **2.5 Water samples collection and chemical analysis**

136 Along with the collection of plastic items, lake surface water was sampled to analyse the physicochemical conditions and the
137 metal concentration in the water phase, potentially affecting sorption processes. Physicochemical parameters (pH,
138 temperature, and electrical conductivity) were measured *in situ* using handheld probes (HI 9025 pH meter and HI 9033
139 conductivity meter, HANNA Instruments, Italy). For metal analyses, water samples were directly filtered *in situ* and stored in
140 pre-cleaned LDPE bottles (Nalgene®).⁶¹ These bottles were kept in the dark and transported to the laboratory, where samples
141 were stored in a refrigerator at 4 °C. The analysis of trace elements was done via ICP-MS, as explained in section 2.3. Before
142 ICP-MS analysis, samples were acidified by addition of 2% v/v ultra-pure distilled nitric acid. Samples were analysed in three

143 replicates, monitoring the relative standard deviation (RSD) to be below $\pm 5\%$. Major anions and cations (F^- , Cl^- , Br^- , NO_3^- , PO_4^{3-} ,
144 SO_4^{2-} , Li^+ , Na^+ , NH_4^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , and Ca^{2+}) were, instead, determined through ion chromatography (Eco IC Metrohm,
145 Switzerland). More details concerning water sampling methods, analysis and QA/QC protocols are reported elsewhere.⁶²

146

147 **2.6 Reagents, QA/QC protocols and data analysis**

148 Quality control (QA/QC) measures were applied to ensure reliable and accurate measurements of metals. First, all operations
149 were carried out under a linear flow hood to avoid airborne contamination (aura HZ72T BIOAIR, Italy). The solutions were
150 prepared from analytical grade reagents and ultrapure water (obtained by a Sartorius Arium® mini, Germany; resistivity: 18.8
151 $M\cdot\Omega\cdot cm$; TOC: <5 ppb). Ultrapure nitric acid 67-69% was produced through purification of analytical grade acid (Carlo Erba
152 reagents, Italy) using subboiling distillation in a Milestone (USA) DuoPur system.⁶³ Ammonium nitrate solution was prepared
153 by dissolution of its crystalline salt (Carlo Erba reagents, Italy). Acetic acid solution was obtained from dilution of glacial acetic
154 acid (Carlo Erba reagents, Italy), while hydrogen peroxide 30% v/v was purchased as it is (Sigma-Aldrich, USA). Before use, all
155 the lab containers were cleaned with a detergent solution (NALGENE® L900) first, then soaked in a 2% nitric acid bath, washed
156 with ultrapure water, and lastly air dried under a laminar flow hood. To assure precision and accuracy in the quantification
157 during ICP-MS analysis, a multi element standard was used for external calibration. This was prepared by dilution of Sigma-
158 Aldrich (USA) multi-elemental standard. Analytical blanks were employed to take any source of possible contamination into
159 account.

160 All the measurements were performed in replicates to determine their uncertainty. Method Detection Limits (MDL) were
161 estimated using method blanks: they were calculated as the mean determined concentration plus three times the standard
162 deviation of a set of method blanks. During data analysis, values which were below the method detection limits were
163 substituted with MDL/2 value.⁶⁴

164 The final data were reported as μg of the extracted metal by unit of volume (cm^3) of the dry sample. This method of displaying
165 results allowed all values coming from different polymer types to be compared among each other. To this end, reference
166 density values chosen for weight-to-volume conversions were $0.94 \mu g/cm^3$ for PE, $0.90 \mu g/cm^3$ for PP and $1.41 \mu g/cm^3$ for
167 PET.⁶⁵

168 To evaluate the available fractions (extractable from the surface) against the total metal quantities in different samples,
169 extraction ratios were calculated as follows:

$$170 \quad \text{Extraction ratio [\%]} = \frac{[M]_{surface}}{[M]_{total}} * 100$$

171 where $[M]_{surface}$ is the concentration of the extracted metal with a specific extraction protocol, whereas $[M]_{total}$ represents
172 the total concentration of the same metal determined through acid digestion procedure.

173 Descriptive statistics (25th – 75th percentiles, median and maximum) were applied to summarize the dataset regarding acid
174 digestion, 2% HNO₃ extraction and sequential extractions for all samples. Calculations and other statistics (non-parametric
175 Mann-Whitney test) were performed with Origin 2018 software (OriginLab Corporation, Northampton, MA, USA).

Fig. 2 Average extraction ratios of the labile metals associated to plastic samples. Panel a) shows the differences in environmental and virgin samples, while panel b) shows the differences among different polymer types. Significantly different data ($p < 0.05$) after Mann-Whitney test are indicated by an asterisk.

176 3 Results and discussion

177 3.1 Total and extractable concentrations of metals from plastic samples

178 The total load of metals in the samples showed pronounced variability with concentrations ranging from values greater than
179 1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ to values below the limit of detection (Table S1 and Fig. S1). Specifically, metals such as Sn, Fe, Al, Ba and Zn
180 were detected at the highest concentrations (average values ranged from $\sim 10 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ to $\sim 200 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$), Mn, Cu, Sr and Ti
181 exhibited one order of magnitude lower levels (average values from $\sim 1 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ to $\sim 10 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$), while Ni, Pb, As, Cr, Ag, Co,
182 V, Cd and U were less abundant (averagely below $1 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$, Table S1). This heterogenous trend was also observed in virgin
183 samples: no statistically meaningful differences in the total metal concentration were observed between environmental and
184 pristine samples for most of the analysed elements (Mn and Pb were the only two exceptions, Fig. S1). The high total
185 concentrations of several metals in virgin samples indicate the use of inorganic and metal-organic additives and fillers in the
186 formulation of plastic items (see detailed discussion in section 3.4).

187 High variance of total metals in environmental plastics was reported for other freshwater settings.^{39,49} Variance in metal
188 content can stem from sample polymer type and level of ageing, environmental conditions of the sampling areas and
189 extraction methods used for metal quantification. This high variance also hampers a proper comparison with our data. These
190 outcomes confirm the great chemical heterogeneity of plastic materials, as well as the complexity of the interactions with
191 other chemicals they are exposed in the environment.

192 The extraction ratios measured through data from the single extraction (HNO₃ 2%, targeting loosely bound metals on the
193 surface of the objects) revealed instead a clearer trend. Environmental samples of every polymer displayed, in fact, generally
194 higher extraction ratios compared to virgin samples for the corresponding metals, with significant differences for 8 of the
195 analysed metals (i.e., Sn, Al, Mn, Pb, Ti, Co, V and U, Fig. 2a). Considering the environmental samples, Sn, Pb, Mn and U were
196 the metals desorbing from the surface in a greater quantity relatively to their total content (extraction ratios ranged from
197 30% to 90%). By contrast, other metals yielded <10% in extraction ratios (i.e., Fe, Cr, Ag, Cu, Sr and Zn), indicating that they
198 were likely more present (and more strongly retained) in the polymer matrix, most probably already in origin.

199 Ni, Cd and Ba showed instead (not statistically significant) higher values of extraction ratios for virgin plastics in comparison
200 to environmental samples. This observation coincided however with extremely low concentration of these elements in both
201 the total digestion and the direct extraction of several pristine MPs (Table S1), which may more easily lead to an
202 overestimation of the extraction ratios. Considering the absolute values of direct extractions with HNO₃ 2% (Table S2 and Fig.
203 S2), in fact, environmental samples show a significantly higher absolute concentration of these metals in comparison to virgin
204 samples.

205

206 **3.2 Metal fractionation on plastic samples**

207 Sequential extractions provided further insights concerning the fractions of labile metals, helping in discriminating the
208 possible sources of the metals on plastic samples.

209 The discussion of metal fractionation here is limited to the 11 more abundant analysed elements since the others (i.e., Ag,
210 As, Cd, Co, Cr, V, U) presented values below the detection limits for more than 50% of the samples, hampering a significant
211 comparison of data. Expectedly, as for other extractions, there were marked differences between environmental and pristine
212 plastic samples (Fig. 3 and Table S2). Virgin samples yielded lower concentrations of metals in all the three extraction steps
213 (Fig. 3a) in comparison to environmental samples (Fig. 3b) for most of the analysed elements, with the exceptions of Cu and
214 Zn. Results were in line with concentrations obtained from HNO₃ 2% single-step extraction.

215 The fractionation pattern of the metals differed between virgin and environmental samples, too. In the case of virgin samples,
216 the second extraction step (acetic acid 0.1M) provided higher quantities for most metals (Mn, Cu, Pb and Ti were the only
217 exceptions), whereas the third extraction step (hydrogen peroxide 30% v/v) yielded the lowest amounts (or below detection
218 limits), with the only exception of Ti. Environmental samples showed, instead, several changes in metal fractionation. For
219 example, the third extraction step produced a significant increase in the case of Sn, Fe, Al and Zn: this effect could be due to
220 the sorption of metals in the organic matter (or biofilms) present on the surface of plastics obtained from the environment,
221 and absent on pristine plastics.⁶⁶⁻⁶⁸ In addition, other metals such as Ni and Sr showed higher concentrations in the first step
222 (which extracted metals bonded through more labile forms of bonding compared to the other steps). For Al, Fe, Zn and Pb
223 instead the extraction step with acetic acid yielded the highest amount of metals. These results were in line with previous
224 studies, indicating a pH-dependant leaching of these metals.^{25,27,69} The high variability of changes in metal fractionation
225 proves again that plastic-metals interactions are complex processes, both dependant on metal properties (e.g., the source as
226 additive or the sorption in the environment and its chemical properties) and the environmental conditions.

227

228 **3.3 The role of polymer type and ageing in regulating plastic-metal interactions**

229 The differences observed between environmental and pristine samples indicate that MPs environmental ageing processes
230 are key in defining metal sorption-desorption equilibria, confirming the results of other case studies investigating MP-metals
231 interactions.⁷⁰⁻⁷⁴ The physiochemical characterization of the plastic samples helped in shading light on the factors affecting
232 sorption-desorption processes.

233 FTIR analysis guided the identification of the polymers composing the environmental and pristine samples (i.e., PE, PP and
 234 PET, Fig. S3) through the analysis of the fingerprinting absorption bands (Table S3). These polymers are indeed the most used

Fig. 3 Speciation of the labile metals obtained with the three-step extraction scheme. Average values of the three metal fractions distinguished for virgin (Panel a) and environmental (Panel b) samples are reported. Results for Ag, As, Cd, Co, Cr, V, U are not shown since more than 50% of the samples were below MDL.

235 in everyday items (PE and PP are the two most manufactured types worldwide), as also found in other settings.⁷⁵ In addition,
 236 the abundance of PE and PP is representative of beached litter, which is generally composed by low density floating polymers
 237 transported by surface currents and winds in freshwater bodies.⁵⁵

238 The FTIR spectra of environmental samples showed some clear changes in functional groups induced by the environmental
 239 ageing of polymers in comparison to virgin samples.⁷⁶ The changes in the indexes for specific aging bands are shown in Fig.
 240 4: the main variations were observed in the regions of hydroxyl (3600 – 3000 cm⁻¹) and carbonyl groups (1300 – 1000 cm⁻¹),
 241 confirming the superficial oxidation due to a series of co-occurring environmental processes, such as UV exposure,

Fig. 4 SEM images of one virgin (a, c, e) versus one environmental (b, d, f) sample for every polymer type (i.e., PE, PP and PET) at 2000X magnification.

242 atmospheric oxygen and thermal effects. This is particularly evident for polymers with mainly aliphatic chains like PE and PP.
243 These changes in functional groups on the surface of polymers may affect metal sorption, with the potential development of
244 either coordination complexes or non-covalent interactions.^{2,38,77} In addition, these changes increase polymer wettability,
245 facilitating the release of metal-containing additives.^{70,78} Another process that can modify polymer FTIR spectra is
246 biofouling.^{66,67} The presence of a biofilm on the environmental samples can be inferred from characteristic absorption peaks
247 indicative of either proteins (1650 cm^{-1} and 1550 cm^{-1} regions, respectively for amide I and II stretching), or polysaccharides
248 (1040 cm^{-1} band of C-O stretching).⁷⁹ These bands were noticeable in 2 out of 6 environmental samples (PEenv3 and PPen2,
249 respectively), while clearly lacking in virgin samples. These two samples, in fact, showed higher concentrations of Al, Mn, Fe
250 and Pb compared to most of the other pristine and environmental samples in the most labile fractions (steps 1 and 2, Table
251 S2). This organic layer may play a pivotal role in the sorption of metals from the environment and in the potential release of
252 additives. The different surface groups may induce chemical sorption of several metals (e.g., through complexation with
253 extracellular polysaccharides), while microorganisms may also actively absorb metals from water in solution.^{66,67,80–82} Biofilms
254 may mediate metal additive release from plastic, too.⁸³ Unfortunately, the lack of a quantitative analysis of biofilm coverage
255 on plastic hampered a clear assessment of this process in our study.

256 Beyond surface functional groups, environmental ageing of plastic affected the surface micromorphology of the generated
257 MPs. SEM images (Fig. 5) showed, in fact, evident differences between the images of virgin samples and environmental
258 samples, regardless of the type of polymer composing the sample. The surfaces of pristine samples appeared smooth and
259 homogeneous, with limited irregularities, whereas those of environmental samples were typically rugged, wrinkled, with
260 several evident pits and cracks. Another noteworthy feature of environmental samples was the presence of filamentous-
261 shaped structures covering the surfaces (shown in Fig. 5d and 5f), which may indicate the residuals of a biofilm layer on
262 plastics. These changes may indeed increase both sorption of metals from the environment and the release of metal additives
263 due to the increase of the specific surface area of MP fragments, as already largely documented in prior studies.^{23,27,49,84}

264

265 **3.4 Assessing the potential sources of elements in plastic**

Fig. 5 Indexes of IR bands for the different polymer types: PE (a); PP (b); PET (c). Environmental samples (env) and virgin samples (vir) are displayed. Indexes referred to amides (1650 cm^{-1}), polysaccharides (1040 cm^{-1}), hydroxyl (3500 cm^{-1}) and carbonyl groups (1715 cm^{-1}).

266 The combination of the information obtained by the analysis of total, acid extractable and sequentially extracted metals on
 267 the plastic samples helped in assessing the origin of metals in the samples, while the characterization of plastic samples and
 268 the analysis of the freshwater body gave insights on the chemical composition of plastic and chemical conditions affecting
 269 sorption-desorption processes. The analysis of available concentration of these elements in water samples may further help
 270 in investigating which metals were potentially enriched from the environment (Table S4 and Table S5).

271

272 **3.4.1 Environmental enrichment in metals.** Metals as Fe, Al, Mn, Zn, Sr and Pb showed an (although not exclusively)
 273 enrichment likely due to metal sorption from the environment. Several of these metals (i.e., Sn, Al, Mn and Pb) showed, in
 274 fact, a significantly higher extraction ratio by HNO_3 2% extractions in environmental samples compared to the virgin ones
 275 (Fig. 2a). This information alone, however, can also indicate that metals present as additives are more easily leached in
 276 environmental samples due to aging.⁸⁵

277 The changes in metal fractionation between virgin and environmental samples can give further insights for understanding
 278 their origin. For example, Fe, Mn, Zn and Al exhibited a marked increase in the third extraction step, indicating a strong effect
 279 of the organic layer or the biofilm formed on plastic in the sorption of these metals from the environment. The high

280 concentration of these elements in this step for the samples PEenv3 and PPEenv2, which showed also higher absorbance in
281 the bands representing biofilms (Fig. 4), further corroborates this hypothesis.

282 For Pb and Mn a significantly higher concentration was observed in environmental samples by acid digestion, too. The
283 significantly higher total concentration further suggests an enrichment in these elements on the surface of environmental
284 plastic in comparison with virgin samples.

285 Some of the abovementioned metals were also abundant in the water of Como Bay (e.g., Sr: 146.39 µg/l; Zn: 20.90 µg/l; Al:
286 15.8 µg/l; Fe: 3.14 µg/l), which is consistent with the hypothesis of their prevailing environmental origin.

287

288 **3.4.2 Potential origin of metals as additives.** Information concerning the potential presence of metals as additives in plastics
289 can be obtained considering the most recalcitrant fraction, especially the total digestion of plastic samples. Some of the
290 analysed metals showed values of extraction ratios below 10% in environmental samples (e.g., Cu, Ti and Ba, Fig. 2a). These
291 elements may be mostly originated from additives within the polymeric matrix. They did not show any noticeable changes
292 between virgin and environmental samples in extraction ratios and in the total concentration after acid digestion. Cu, in
293 addition, presented higher concentration values from sequential extraction for virgin samples than environmental ones,
294 further confirming its presence as additive. This element is often added to plastic polymers as a dye and as biocide.^{86,87} Ba
295 showed, instead, higher values for the most labile fraction in environmental samples. This is probably due to its very high
296 concentration in an environmental sample only (PPEenv2, Table S2). Ba is in fact commonly added to plastic as a stabilizer,
297 filler and dye (usually as barium sulphate, barytes).⁸⁸ Ti as well, did not show significant changes in the extraction ratios and
298 in the fractionation pattern, highlighting a main source as plastic additive. Its presence is linked to the use of TiO₂, often
299 added as a dye or UV absorber to prolong polymer life and delay ageing. TiO₂ dispersion in the environment after plastic
300 weathering is an already known environmental process.^{39,89}

301 Some metals with potential enrichment from the environment show low extraction ratios in environmental samples, too (i.e.,
302 Zn, Al, Zn, Fe and Sr). All these metals also showed non-significant differences in the total concentration from acid digestion
303 between environmental and virgin samples (Fig. S1). These elements may therefore have a contribution also from the plastic
304 polymer matrix, indicating a mixed source (i.e., a contribution of both sorption from the environment and additive leaching)
305 in environmental samples.

306 As a final note, the linkage between plastic colours and metals content indicated the extensive use of metal-based pigments
307 for plastic products. Fe, Cd, Zn, Cr and Cu are in fact usually employed as pigments. For example, Pb and Ba are used for the
308 yellow, while Cu, Pb and Cr based pigments are, instead, often mixed to obtain darker variants.^{25,90} This is evident observing
309 the acid digestion results of our samples: the blue and green PPEvir1 and PPEenv2 showed high abundance of Fe, Zn, Cu, Ba and
310 Cr compared to other samples (Table S1). This is also in accordance with other reports.^{19,21,91} In our study we also assessed
311 an increase in the concentration of these elements in the most labile fraction too (i.e., the step 1 of the sequential extraction).
312 This evidence clearly shows that plastic ageing processes possibly also make matrix-bonded metals more likely to be released,
313 and, in turn, more bioavailable.

314

315 **3.2 Lessons learned in this study towards a refined risk assessment of metals and environmental plastics**

316 The combination of different analytical approaches in this study helped gaining insights on the origin of metals in
317 environmental plastic. This approach can improve the understanding of sorption/desorption processes from the environment
318 and help investigating the likelihood of additive release during plastic environmental ageing. This in turn can help improving
319 assessment of the risk of MPs as metal vectors.^{37,71,92–94}

320 The results observed from the acid digestion of plastic samples in our study (section 3.1) showed, instead, that the total load
321 of metals is often similar in virgin and environmental samples. This indicates a potential overestimation of the risk when
322 exposure assessment is based upon the total acid digestion data:^{95,96} the potential bioavailability of the metals strongly
323 bonded within the polymer matrix relies on the kinetics of additive release, the polymer type and the grade of environmental
324 ageing.⁹⁷

325 Results of this study also remark the complexity of plastic-metal interactions in the environment. Beside the complete
326 analytical assessment of the selected environmental samples, the trends observed varied greatly. This indicates that the
327 environmental risk posed by plastic-metal interactions is driven by several factors at stake, such as the chemical property of
328 the metal, polymer type, degree of ageing and the water chemical conditions. The assessment of the origin and,
329 consequently, the potential availability of metals in plastic are therefore far from straightforward. As a further complication,
330 in our case study several metals (e.g., Al, Fe, Sn, Sr) not surprisingly showed a possible mixed origin.
331 The results of this study also highlight the increase in concentration of metals in the extractable phases in environmental
332 samples compared to virgin ones, regardless of their origin. The processes of environmental ageing are key to affect the
333 potential bioavailability of metals on plastic, both by increasing the sorption capacity of metals and promoting the release of
334 additives from the polymeric matrix. Therefore, we suggest future studies assessing the potential confounding factors in
335 more simplified systems (e.g., micro- or mesocosms) in order to potentially test the effects of different factors in more
336 controllable and tuneable conditions (e.g., adding plastic with known amount of metal additives).

337 4 Conclusions

338 In this study we examined metals associated to beached plastics sampled from Lake Como shores. We applied a multi-tiered
339 analytical approach to differentiate the origin of metals on environmental plastic samples, possibly discerning the metals
340 enriched by sorption processes and the additives released by plastic polymers. The analysis of the total concentration, the
341 labile fraction and the different fractionation by extraction techniques shed light on the speciation of metals in different
342 samples and the comparison between differences in environmental samples and virgin plastic objects helped in assessing the
343 background concentrations of metals in plastic polymers.

344 The combination of these information also helped in understanding the more likely origin of the analysed metals in the
345 environmental samples: Mn and Pb were mostly enriched from the environment; Ba, Cu and Ti were mainly released from
346 the polymer matrix; and Zn, Sn, Sr, Fe and Al were likely originated from a mixed source.

347 This study also showed that environmental samples generally present higher concentration of labile metals, which indicates
348 a potential increased environmental risk of metal bonded to plastic induced by polymer ageing processes. The sequential
349 extraction results also indicated an increase of several metals (e.g., Al, Fe, Zn) in the organic matter bonded fraction,
350 confirming the important role of organic matter and biofilms in mediating the sorption process of metals from the
351 environment. Overall, our findings highlighted the role of plastics as potential carriers for the transfer of metals in freshwater
352 media and confirmed that field studies can give important insights for the environmental risk related with this issue.

353 Author Contributions

354 **Conceptualization:** SC, GB (Gilberto Binda); **Methodology:** SC, DS, DM, GB (Gilberto Binda); **Investigation:** SC, DS, GB (Ginevra
355 Boldrocchi); **Data curation:** SC, AP, RB; **Writing (Original draft):** SC; **Writing (Review and editing):** AP, DS, DM, RB, GB (Ginevra
356 Boldrocchi), LN, GB (Gilberto Binda); **Supervision:** AP, RB, LN; **Funding acquisition:** LN, GB (Gilberto Binda).

357 Conflicts of interest

358 There are no conflicts to declare.

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